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INVESTIGATION OF RADIOLOGICAL HAZARD INDICES IN SOIL SAMPLES COLLECTED FROM QUARRY SITES IN ITU, AKWA IBOM STATE, NIGERIA.

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Abstract

Investigation of radiological hazard indices in soil samples collected from quarry sites of Ayadehe and Oku Iboku in Itu Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria have been conducted. The activity concentration of the radionuclides in the samples range from 166.86 ± 1.65 Bq/Kg to 281.59 ± 2.23 Bq/Kg with a mean of 226.52 ± 1.95 Bq/Kg for ^{40}K , from 2.7 ± 0.06 Bq/Kg to 6.91 ± 0.1 Bq/Kg with a mean of 4.56 ± 0.08 Bq/Kg for ^{238}U and from 1.51 ± 0.08 Bq/Kg to 4.78 ± 0.08 Bq/Kg with an average of 3.39 ± 0.07 Bq/Kg for ^{232}Th . These values are within the recommended safety limits of 400 Bq/Kg, 35 Bq/Kg and 30 Bq/Kg for ^{40}K , ^{238}U and ^{232}Th respectively. Also, the radium equivalent ranges in value from 22.27 Bq/Kg to 34.08 Bq/Kg with mean of 26.86 Bq/Kg which below the safety limit of 370 Bq/Kg. The average values of absorbed dose rate, annual effective dose equivalent, external hazard index, internal hazard index and excess lifetime cancer risk obtained are 13.93 nGyh^{-1} , 0.0855 mSvy^{-1} , 0.6301, 0.0854 and 0.2992×10^{-3} respectively. These values are within the world recommended safety limit values as published by (UNSCEAR, 2000). This shows that the area under investigation is not significantly affected radiologically.

Key words: Radioactivity level, hazard indices, soil.

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1.0 INTRODUCTION

Human environment is filled with both natural and artificial radionuclides that continuously disintegrate to release radioactive particles into the environment (Buket, et al. 2010). Human beings therefore are daily exposed to radiation from several sources that depend upon their activities and environment and lot of contaminants in human environment have attracted serious concern in research community all around the world (Oladejo et al., 2010). This concern is due to the environmental and health consequences associated with its exposure, largely at levels above the recommended safety limits. Not every source of radiation exposure affects the entire global population (Mahapatra, 2023). For instance, those who work in the nuclear sector or who are treated through medical irradiation will be exposed to radiation rather than the general public. Natural ionizing radiation, which is produced by naturally occurring radionuclides in the environment, is one of the most visible sources to which everyone is inescapably and continuously exposed (UNSCEAR, 2000). Most of the time, this exposure poses little to no risk to society, but in some circumstances, it is necessary to take health protection measures into account. Naturally Occurring Radioactive Materials (NORMs), which is present both at the surface of the earth and in the subsurface, is the primary source of natural radiation in the environment.

According to UNSCEAR (1988), naturally occurring radioactive materials (NORMs) are responsible for around 70% of the world's population's exposure to ionizing radiation. Since the earth's creation, NORM have played a significant role in the human environment. In specific locations or localities, however, their presence may be at increased levels, creating the possibility of exposure conditions (Kathren, 1998; Jacob et al, 1986). Natural radioactivity is wide spread in the earth's environment and it exists in various geological formations in soil, sand, rocks, plants, water and air. The natural radioactivity in soil or sand comes from ^{40}K , ^{238}U and ^{232}Th . Artificial radionuclides can also be present such as ^{137}Cs , resulting from the fallout from weapons testing (Emad, et al.,2022). The radiological implication of these radionuclides is due to the gamma ray exposure of the body and irradiation of lung tissue from inhalation of radon and its daughters. The tissues of the human body are known to suffer clinical harm from high amounts of radioactive material exposure (Briggs-Kamara and Erundu,2012). External exposure to gamma rays, internal exposure through inhaled radon and its decay products, inhalation of contaminated dust, and ingestion of contaminated food and water are some possible exposure routes from these nuclides (Einsbeid, 1987). Activities of man such as mining, tailing, quarry, land excavation has contributed to a greater percentage of exposure and health hazards of gamma radiations (EL-Arabi, 2005).

Due to the economic values and high demands for quarry products such as sand, gravels, laterite, and clay, some geographical areas of Itu Local Government like Ayadehe and Oku Iboku which are naturally endowed with the abundance of these resources are now witnessing increase commercial quarry and excavation activities by some of the inhabitants of the area who considered such activities as their primary source of living (Essien and Emmanuel, 2016). Quarry activities has the potential of increasing radiation exposure to the environment (Tsai et al,2008)

Therefore, the assessment of gamma radiation dose from natural sources is of particular importance as natural radiation is the largest contributor to the external dose of the world population (UNSCEAR, 1988). Investigation of radiological hazard indices in soil samples collected from quarry sites of Ayadehe and Oku Iboku in Itu, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria to assess the level of natural radioactivity due to gamma rays from the dose rate is needed to implement precautionary measures whenever the dose is found to be above the recommended limits.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Study Area

The study was carried out at Ayadehe and Oku Iboku communities in Itu Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom state, Nigeria. The two areas are riverine which share boundaries with Odukpani Local Government Area of Cross River State and Afaha Itam in Itu Local Government Area. The major occupation of people in the areas are farming, quarry and fishing. Quarry is done in commercial quantity since it serves as a source for road construction and building materials such as gravels, sand and laterite. The climate of the study area is an equatorial climate consisting of two major seasons; the rainy season (which usually starts from March and ends in October) and the dry season (which is from November to February) each year. There is no sharp boundary between these seasons. The rainfall in the study area is heavy with the mean monthly rainfall of about 135mm and 65mm during dry season (Igbokwe et al., 2004)

The coordinates of the sampling points within the area of the study are in Table 1 and geographical map of the study area is shown in Figure 1.

2.2 Samples collection

A total of 30 soil samples were collected from the two quarry sites of Ayadehe and Oku Iboku. At position where the samples were taken, the soil surface were cleared of debris, pebbles, vegetation and roots. Soil samples of about 2.0 kg were collected from each soil position using a shovel and at a depth of 30 – 40 cm and immediately stored in polythene bags to ensure that the radon gas does not escape from the samples (Samuel, 2018)

Figure 1: Geographical map of the Area

Table 1: Coordinates of sample Position

S/N	Sample code	Location	
1.	OK 1	5.158573°	8.056067°
2.	OK 2	5.147482°	8.057113°
3.	OK 3	5.152473°	8.054328°
4.	OK 4	5.148014°	8.055625°
5.	OK 5	5.157723°	8.054832°
6.	OK 6	5.148643°	8.054923°
7.	OK 7	5.15672°	8.054887°
8.	OK 8	5.14930°	8.055386°
9.	OK 9	5.156782°	8.0567223°
10.	OK10	5.148862°	8.054832°
11.	OK 11	5.153261°	8.053493°
12.	OK 12	5.146232°	8.053685°
13.	OK 13	5.157643°	8.055638°
14.	OK 14	5.148844°	8.045673°
15.	OK 15	5.158463°	8.056115°
16.	AY 16	5.032261°	7.972322°
17.	AY 17	5.031163°	7.968324°
18.	AY 18	5.034462°	7.974234°
19.	AY 19	5.033426°	7.968233°
20.	AY 20	5.034377°	7.971456°
21.	AY 21	5.034245°	7.973348°
22.	AY 22	5.034116°	7.969246°
23.	AY 23	5.034266°	7.973614°
24.	AY 24	5.034234°	7.974733°
25.	AY 25	5.032336°	7.974663°
26.	AY 26	5.033413°	7.969435°
27.	AY 27	5.034223°	7.967346°
28.	AY 28	5.032674°	7.972463°
29.	AY 29	5.034334°	7.973246°
30.	AY 30	5.033422°	7.968324°

2.3 Samples Preparation

The collected soil samples were first dried in the sun and then grounded using mortar and pestle and passed through a sieve of 1.0 mm mesh size to separate the coarse particles from the needed fine-grained powder. The sample of each fine gained powder were dried in an oven to about 110°C to ensure total removal of moisture from the samples (Ajayi, 2009). Each prepared sample were weighed 200 g and were transferred to clean transparent plastic containers of uniform area and sealed for four weeks to allow the ²²²Rn and its short-lived daughters to secular equilibrium before spectrometric analysis (Gbadebo, 2011).

2.4 Determination of Radioactivity in the Samples

The radioactivity level was determined in each sample using a well calibrated NaI(Tl) and well shielded detector couple to a computer resident quantum MCA200R:1 Multichannel analyzer. Each sample was placed vertically in the detector and counted for 10 hours (36000 seconds). The 1460KeV gamma-radiation of ⁴⁰K was used to determine the concentration of ⁴⁰K in the sample (J The gamma transition line of 1764KeV ²¹⁴Bi was to determine the activity concentration of the

^{238}U while the gamma transition line of 2614KeV ^{208}Tl was used to determine the concentration of ^{232}Th radionuclide. The activity concentration of the radionuclides (A) in Bq/kg in the samples after decay correction was calculated using the equation below (Avwiri, et al., 2014).

$$A_s = \frac{C_a}{\epsilon_r \times M_s \times t_c \times P_r}$$

Where A_s is the activity concentration in Bq/kg, C_a is the net peak area of a peak energy, ϵ_r is the efficiency of the detector, M_s is mass of the sample, t_c is the total counting time and P_r is the abundance of the Y-line in a radionuclide.

2.4.1 Absorbed Dose Rate

The effect of gamma radiation arising from radioactive sources in the environment is given in terms of the total gamma radiation absorbed dose rate in air. The absorbed dose rate is calculated using equation below (Tzortzis et al., 2003)

$$D_Y(\text{nGyh}^{-1}) = 0.427A_u + 0.662A_{th} + 0.043A_k$$

2.4.2 Annual Effective Dose Equivalent

The annual effective dose equivalent measured in mSvy^{-1} , received by individuals exposed to radiation is obtained using the equation below (Muhammad et al., 2024)

$$D_{out}(\text{mSvy}^{-1}) = D_Y(\text{nGyh}^{-1}) \times 24\text{hrs} \times 365.23\text{d} \times 0.2 \times 0.7\text{SvGy}^{-1} \times 10^{-6}$$

2.4.3 External and Internal Hazard Indices

The radon and its short-lived products are hazardous to the respiratory organs and as a result, the internal exposure to radon and its daughter products is quantified using the internal hazard index is obtained using the equation below.

$$H_{in} = \frac{A_u}{185} + \frac{A_{th}}{259} + \frac{A_k}{4810}$$

Also, the external hazard index which must be less than unity for the radiation hazard to be considered negligible can be obtained using the equation below

$$H_{ex} = \frac{A_u}{370} + \frac{A_{th}}{259} + \frac{A_k}{4810}$$

Where A_u , A_{th} and A_k are the activity concentration of the radionuclides of uranium-238, thorium-232 and potassium-40 respectively (Darwish, et al., 2015).

2.4.4 Excess lifetime Cancer Risk (ELCR)

The excess lifetime cancer risk which gives the probability of an individual developing cancer due to the exposure to radiation sources is calculated using the equation below

$$\text{ELCR} = D_{out} \times D_L \times R_f$$

Where D_L is the duration of lifetime (taken approximately 70 years), D_{out} is the annual effective dose equivalent and R_f is the risk factor which reflects the total cancer risk per sievert (Bajwa et al., 2017).

3.0. Results and Discussion

The activity concentrations of the radionuclides in the soil samples and the radiological hazard are given in Tables 2 and 3.

Table 2: Activity concentration of Radionuclides.

Sample code	⁴⁰ KBq/Kg	²³⁸ U Bq/Kg	²³² Th Bq/Kg
OK01	262.7±2.15	4.62±0.08	4.19±0.08
OK02	281.59±2.23	6.31±0.09	4.26±0.08
OK03	242.78±2.05	4.25±0.07	3.29±0.07
OK04	240.77±2.04	5.28±0.08	3.3±0.07
OK05	242.98±2.05	4.63±0.08	3.41±0.07
OK06	239.58±2.04	2.91±0.06	2.88±0.06
OK07	239.12±2.03	4.16±0.07	3.18±0.07
OK08	189.61±1.78	4.46±0.08	3.47±0.07
OK09	223.3±1.96	4.64±0.08	3.57±0.07
OK10	166.86±1.65	3.7±0.07	2.54±0.08
OK11	225.9±1.97	3.56±0.07	2.43±0.08
OK12	243.22±2.05	3.82±0.07	1.51±0.08
OK13	231.12±2.0	2.7±0.06	1.71±0.08
OK14	220.71±1.94	5.28±0.08	3.97±0.07
OK15	236.45±2.02	5.63±0.09	4.03±0.08
AY16	247.02±2.07	6.11±0.09	3.27±0.07
AY17	240.91±2.04	5.49±0.09	3.25±0.07
AY18	245.19±2.06	4.66±0.08	3.12±0.07
AY19	235.4±2.02	4.52±0.08	4.27±0.08
AY20	204.99±1.86	4.99±0.08	3.11±0.06
AY21	227.98±1.86	6.91±0.1	3.18±0.07
AY22	222.68±1.95	5.47±0.09	4.43±0.08
AY23	240.55±2.04	5.62±0.09	4.32±0.08
AY24	209.71±1.89	5.17±0.07	3.28±0.07
AY25	182.86±1.74	4.03±0.08	3.14±0.07
AY26	222.6±1.95	2.16±0.06	2.08±0.06
AY27	202.76±1.85	4.08±0.08	4.47±0.08
AY28	194.07±1.8	4.51±0.08	4.78±0.08
AY29	189.61±1.78	3.73±0.07	3.65±0.07
AY30	242.6±2.05	3.59±0.07	3.71±0.07
Mean	226.52±1.95	4.56±0.08	3.39±0.07

Table 3. The radiological hazard indices obtained for the study area

D_Y (nGyh ⁻¹)						ELCR($\times 10^{-4}$)
Sample	¹⁾	Ra_{eq} (Bq/Kg)	Hin	Hex	D(mSvy ⁻¹)	³⁾
OK01	16.04	30.84	0.0964	0.7282	0.0984	0.3445
OK02	17.62	34.08	0.1098	0.7858	0.1081	0.3784
OK03	14.43	27.65	0.0867	0.6728	0.0885	0.3099
OK04	14.79	28.54	0.0919	0.6714	0.0907	0.3176
OK05	14.68	28.22	0.0893	0.6748	0.0900	0.3153
OK06	13.45	25.48	0.0772	0.6588	0.0825	0.2888
OK07	14.16	27.12	0.0850	0.6625	0.0869	0.3041
OK08	12.35	24.02	0.0774	0.5300	0.0758	0.2653
OK09	13.95	26.94	0.0858	0.6217	0.0855	0.2995
OK10	10.44	20.18	0.0649	0.4655	0.0640	0.2241
OK11	12.82	24.37	0.0758	0.6210	0.0786	0.2752
OK12	13.08	24.69	0.0774	0.6718	0.0802	0.2809
OK13	12.22	22.94	0.0697	0.6349	0.0750	0.2625
OK14	14.37	27.95	0.0903	0.6173	0.0881	0.3086
OK15	15.23	29.57	0.0956	0.6611	0.0934	0.3270
AY16	15.40	29.81	0.0976	0.6915	0.0944	0.3306
AY17	14.85	28.69	0.0929	0.6725	0.0911	0.3190
AY18	14.60	28.00	0.0888	0.6808	0.0895	0.3135
AY19	14.88	28.75	0.0904	0.6541	0.0913	0.3195
AY20	13.00	25.22	0.0821	0.5736	0.0797	0.2792
AY21	14.86	29.01	0.0975	0.6432	0.0911	0.3191
AY22	14.84	28.95	0.0935	0.6235	0.0910	0.3187
AY23	15.60	30.32	0.0977	0.6723	0.0957	0.3351
AY24	13.39	26.01	0.0847	0.5871	0.0822	0.2877
AY25	11.66	22.60	0.0724	0.5101	0.0715	0.2504
AY26	11.87	22.27	0.0665	0.6099	0.0728	0.2549
AY27	13.41	26.08	0.0820	0.5643	0.0823	0.2882
AY28	13.43	26.29	0.0837	0.5426	0.0824	0.2885
AY29	12.16	23.55	0.0741	0.5273	0.0746	0.2612
AY30	14.42	27.58	0.0848	0.6698	0.0884	0.3097
Mean	13.93	26.86	0.0854	0.6301	0.0855	0.2992

3.1 Activity Concentrations

The activity concentration of the radionuclides in the samples range from 166.86 ± 1.65 Bq/Kg to 281.59 ± 2.23 Bq/Kg with a mean of 226.52 ± 1.95 Bq/Kg for ^{40}K which within the world recommended value of 400 Bq/Kg, the values for ^{238}U range from 2.7 ± 0.06 Bq/Kg to 6.91 ± 0.1 Bq/Kg with a mean of 4.56 ± 0.08 Bq/Kg which within the recommended safety limit of 35 Bq/Kg. The activity concentration varies from

1.51±0.08 Bq/Kg to 4.78±0.08 Bq/Kg with an average of 3.39±0.07 Bq/Kg for ²³²Th which is within the safety limit of 30 Bq/Kg. Also, the radium equivalent ranges in value from 22.27 Bq/Kg to 34.08 Bq/Kg with mean of 26.86 Bq/Kg. This result agrees with the previous study elsewhere within the South South zone of Nigeria (Iwetan, et al 2015, Bede et al 2015). These values compare well with the previous values obtained by Essien and Akpan (2016) with no significant rise in the radioactivity level in the quarry sites.

3.2 Radiological Hazard Indices

The average values of radium equivalent activity Ra_{eq} (Bq/Kg), absorbed dose rate D_Y (nGyh⁻¹), annual effective dose equivalent, $D(mSvy^{-1})$, external hazard index H_{ex} , internal hazard index H_{in} and excess lifetime cancer risk (ELCR) are 26.86 Bq/Kg, 13.93 nGyh⁻¹, 0.0855 mSvy⁻¹, 0.6301, 0.0854 and 0.2992×10^{-3} respectively. These values are within the world recommended safety limit values as published by (UNSCEAR, 2000). The recommended value for radium equivalent is 370 Bq/Kg, for absorbed dose rate is 55 nGyh⁻¹, for annual effective dose equivalent is 1.0 mSvy⁻¹, and for ELCR is 0.29×10^{-3} respectively.

Figure 2: Comparison of hazard indices with standard

Figure 3: Range of Hazard Risk in the Samples

Figure 4: Regression Correlation between Hex and Hin

The mean values of Hex and Hin are less than unity, therefore does not constitute any significant radiological risk to the inhabitant of the area. The comparison of these hazard indices with recommended safety limit is given in Figure 2. Figure 3 shows the range of the radiological hazard index which indicates that none of hazard indices above unity; the recommended safety limit. This indicates that interaction with the soils in the quarry sites will not lead to respiratory diseases such as asthma and cancer and external diseases such as erythema, skin cancer and cataracts (Avwiri et al., 2012). The regression correlation between the internal and external hazard indices gives a regression coefficient of 0.52 which shows that they are not highly correlated linearly as shown in Figure 4.

Conclusion

Investigation of radiological hazard indices in soil samples collected from quarry sites of Oku Iboku and Ayadehe communities in Itu Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria have been conducted. The activity concentrations of ^{40}K , ^{238}U , and ^{232}Th in soil samples of the study area were below their respective world recommended safety limit. The radionuclides are randomly distributed in the soil with ^{40}K being the dominants radionuclide. The calculated radiological hazard indices for the study area are all below their respective world standards. Therefore, quarry activities and the obtained building materials do not pose any significant health threat to the environment and it's residents. However, regular radiation monitoring and evaluation is recommended to check-mate any possible rise in radiation level due to the quarry activities in these areas.

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